

Fertilizer management—organic sources

Influence of green manure (GM) *Sesbania aculeata* on Zn and S translocation in rice

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We evaluated the effect of GM *S. aculeata* on translocation of Zn and S to the grain, straw, and roots of short-duration rice variety ADT36 using ^{65}Zn and ^{35}S radioisotopes in a greenhouse experiment. Zn was applied to soils as ZnSO_4 or EDTA-Zn at 1.0 m Ci/g Zn and S as gypsum at 0.2 m Ci/g S. A black, calcareous clay loam (Vertic Ustropepts) with pH 8.0, EC 0.51 dS/m, 0.56% organic C, 58 ppm total Zn, and 200 ppm total S and a red, noncalcareous sandy loam (Typic Haplustalf) with pH 7.1, EC 0.13 dS/m, 0.45% organic C, 47 ppm total Zn, and 180 ppm total S were used. Recommended levels of NPK were applied.

ZnSO_4 + gypsum + GM recorded the highest percent translocation to the grain of total Zn absorbed in both the clay loam (56.5%) and sandy loam (53.2%) (Table 1). More Zn accumulated in straw with EDTA-Zn than with ZnSO_4 . Zn retention in roots was highest with ZnSO_4 + GM (37.3%) in the clay loam and with EDTA-Zn + GM (49.4%) in the sandy loam. This high retention of Zn in roots without translocation evenly to grain and straw, especially with GM, reflects excessive Zn consumption.

Similarly, an increased translocation to grain of absorbed S occurred with gypsum + GM in both soils, with 42.3% in clay loam and 45.0% in sandy loam (Table 2). Sulfur supplied from the GM might have helped in the higher absorption and translocation of S to grain as compared with its translocation to straw and roots. Information reported is from a tracer study; sufficient replications could not be included to establish facts by statistical significance. ■

Table 1. Percent translocation of ^{65}Zn from applied fertilizer measured at harvest stage.*

Treatment	Clay loam			Sandy loam		
	Grain	Straw	Root	Grain	Straw	Root
ZnSO_4	51.5	22.3	26.3	40.4	32.7	26.9
EDTA-Zn	53.3	27.2	19.6	29.3	41.1	29.5
ZnSO_4 + GM	33.8	29.0	37.3	33.9	27.1	39.0
EDTA-Zn + GM	42.1	31.0	26.8	32.6	18.0	49.4
ZnSO_4 + gypsum + GM	56.5	16.4	27.1	53.2	15.0	28.6

*Mean of two replications. Data not statistically analyzed.

Table 2. Percent translocation of ^{35}S from applied fertilizer measured at harvest stage.*

Treatment	Clay loam			Sandy loam		
	Grain	Straw	Root	Grain	Straw	Root
Gypsum	36.4	40.7	23.0	39.0	49.1	11.9
Gypsum + GM	42.3	39.6	18.2	45.0	41.0	14.1
Gypsum + ZnSO_4 + GM	38.6	42.6	18.9	45.9	40.8	13.2

*Mean of two replications. Data not statistically analyzed.

Biofertilizers enhance dissolved oxygen content (DOC) in water

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Continuous cultivation of blue-green algae (BGA) and azolla is suspected to cause pollution. A study of BGA and azolla nurseries under continuous submergence for more than a year, however, revealed an enhanced DOC in the water. DOC increased between 0600 and 1600 h but declined thereafter.

Between 0600 and 1600 h, DOC ranged from 3.7 to 7.1 ppm in the BGA nursery, from 1.3 to 5.5 ppm in the azolla nursery, and from 3.1 to 5.4 ppm in the control where water was impounded without BGA or azolla. Most samples from the BGA nursery had higher DOC than did those from the control. DOC in the control was higher than that in the azolla nursery, except at 1600 h (Table 1).

CO_2 evolution was 61 mg/h per m^2 in the azolla nursery, which was more than in the BGA nursery (46 mg/h per m^2) and control (10 mg/h per m^2) (Table 2). Although CO_2 emissions may contribute

Table 1. DOC and temperature in BGA and azolla nurseries at TNRRI, Aduthurai, India, Jun-Sep 1992.

Parameter	Sampling time (h)						
	0600	0800	1000	1200	1400	1600	1800
	<i>Dissolved oxygen^a (ppm)</i>						
Control	3.1	5.4	5.3	5.0	5.0	4.7	4.2
BGA nursery	3.7	4.5	6.0	6.8	6.9	7.1	4.2
Azolla nursery	1.3	2.2	3.9	4.2	4.5	5.5	3.3
	<i>Temperature^a (°C)</i>						
Control	25	29	33	38	42	37	32
BGA nursery	25	29	34	38	41	36	32
Azolla nursery	23	28	30	34	39	34	31

*Mean analysis of 2 d.

Table 2. Evolution of CO₂ in BGA and azolla nurseries at TNRRRI, Aduthurai, India, Jun-Sep 1992.

Source	CO ₂ evolved (mg/m ²)	
	12 h ^a	24 h
Control	120 (10) ^b	240 (10)
BGA nursery	550 (46)	1100 (46)
Azolla nursery	480 (40)	1460 (61)

^a0600-1800. ^bFigures in parentheses denote CO₂ evolved (mg/h per m²).

Biomass and N content of *Sesbania rostrata* mutant with long vegetative phase

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TSR-1 (Trombay *S. rostrata*-1), the late-flowering mutant of *S. rostrata*, remains insensitive to critical inductive photoperiod up to 60 d after planting (DAP). It has the potential to produce sufficient biomass regardless of time of sowing.

We evaluated the performance of TSR-1, the parent cultivar, and local

to atmospheric pollution, increased DOC in water associated with biofertilizers might alleviate problems related to stagnant water. Augmenting DOC in continuously submerged fields where BGA and azolla are grown might also eliminate accumulated reduced iron and sulfides, which are toxic to rice. ■

S. aculeata variety during short-day months of Jan and Feb and long-day months of Jun and Jul. *S. sesban* was included in the Jun-Jul study. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design. Net plot size was 2.3 m². Plant height, fresh weight, percent N, and N/plant were determined at 50 DAP.

TSR-1 was significantly superior to its parent and *S. aculeata* for biomass and N/plant during Jan-Feb (Table 1). During Jun-Jul, TSR-1 performed as well as its parent and the other species for all parameters; it had marginal superiority for N/plant (Table 2). TSR-1 can be grown for biomass production during months of long or short photoperiods. ■

Table 1. Data from yield trial of TSR-1, Jan-Feb, Bombay, India.

Variety/species	Plant height (cm)	Fresh weight (kg/plot)	% N (whole plant)	N/plant (g)
<i>S. rostrata</i>	90.0	2.5	3.7	6.12
TSR-1	126.5	4.1	3.6	9.33
<i>S. aculeata</i>	93.5	1.6	3.6	4.19
LSD (0.05)	18.8	0.5	0.7	2.99

Table 2. Data from yield trial of TSR-1, Jun-Jul, Bombay, India.

Variety/species	Plant height (cm)	Fresh weight (kg/plot)	% N		N/plant (g)
			Leaf	Stem	
<i>S. rostrata</i>	187.5	6.1	5.6	1.7	0.92
TSR-1	186.5	6.0	5.4	1.8	1.22
<i>S. sesban</i>	132.3	6.0	5.4	1.4	0.87
<i>S. aculeata</i>	165.3	5.9	5.2	1.9	1.12
LSD (0.01)	33.8	1.6	0.4	0.6	0.38

Integrated pest management—diseases

Analysis of genetic diversity and population structure of bacterial blight (BB) pathogen in West Java, Indonesia

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BB, caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* (Xoo), is the most important disease of lowland rice in Indonesia in the wet season. To develop high-yielding varieties with durable resistance to BB, it is necessary to understand the pathogen population structure. We conducted an initial analysis of genetic diversity and population structure of Xoo in West Java using molecular marker techniques.

1. TNX1 haplotypes defined from the Indonesian Xoo isolates (A-D) and the predominant haplotype (III-B) observed for race 3 in Central Luzon, Philippines. M = DNA molecular weight markers.